

IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7303416>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th October 2022

Accepted: 05th November 2022

Online: 08th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Independent work, higher education, credit-module system, method, technology, result.

ABSTRACT

The credit-module system is a process of organizing education and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit measure. In the credit-module principle, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating. These issues are discussed in the article.

In the credit-module system, students must complete a certain amount of study load in order to achieve study results (credits) in the subjects (modules) specified in the curriculum. In the credit-module system, the ratio of classroom and independent study hours is on average 40% to 60%, that is, for every hour of a lesson in a particular subject, a student needs one and a half hours of independent study outside of class, time for preparation [2].

So, the credit-module teaching system is a system of organizing the process of mastering the educational program, based on the composition of each educational module, and regularly evaluating the knowledge, skills and competencies of students by monitoring the educational results of the module and the final control.

In the credit-module system, students' creative competences such as self-learning, independent search for creative ways of learning, and the pedagogue's ability to provide knowledge based on digital

technologies with a creative approach are developed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Until that time, the main tasks of pedagogues in the higher education system of our country were to search for information in order to impart knowledge and skills to students in certain subjects, assimilation, processing and distribution to students, that is, they performed the task of receiving and transmitting information necessary for the preparation of specialists. The tasks of the students were to learn and acquire knowledge only by participating in the training sessions in the auditoriums and laboratories. They did not pay attention to the formation of independent work skills that help them to perform tasks such as the use of scientific and technical innovations, analytical and logical thinking, and the creation of innovative projects, which are necessary for becoming a mature specialist.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the credit-module system, it is necessary for the student to take responsibility to a certain extent during the course of his education, to work independently in the subject outside the auditorium. Working outside the classroom in the credit-module system requires the teacher to organize the independent work of the student, to provide materials and tools for independent work, and to create effective methods of monitoring the level of student learning. In order to become a specialist, students are required to acquire not only materials and tools, but also experience and skills of independent work that will form the skills of their processing and implementation.

Due to the increase in the share of independent education in the credit-module system, the importance of independent education in the educational process will increase, and this will lead to an increase in independence, creative initiative and activity of specialists in the future, and an innovative and creative attitude in performing any work. The student will always have the opportunity to receive help and advice from the teacher and fellow students. This strengthens mutual cooperation and serves to form teamwork skills, resulting in the development of professional competencies of future specialists.

Due to the widespread use of digital technologies in education, it is difficult to convey all the information to the students only in classroom training in the current environment, where the scope of information and knowledge is expanding rapidly. Therefore, independent education in the credit-module system is an important factor in becoming a modern specialist.

Independent learning is the independent activity of students regularly guided by teachers rather than leaving them to their own devices in imparting knowledge to students. The role of independent education in improving the quality of the educational process is great. The student must understand that independent education is conducted for his benefit. The teacher's cooperation with students in the educational process forms their confidence in independent education. Conducting lectures in a traditional way, i.e., not limited to providing information, but in a problematic interactive way, leads to the expected positive results [3]. The independent work of the learner means that he is responsible for his acquired knowledge and ensures his future professional success. In many cases, the concepts of self-employment and self-employment are used interchangeably, although they have different meanings in the literature. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the content, essence and purpose of these concepts.

Independent work is the scientific information obtained by the student using digital technologies and various technical tools such as software, visual aids, products, in order for the student to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in a specific academic subject outside the classroom under the guidance of the teacher and individually and creatively.

Independent work is an educational activity directed to the student's individual-creative acquisition and improvement of knowledge, skills and abilities in a specific academic subject outside the classroom under the guidance of an educator. The main goal of independent work is not only to

independently perform didactic tasks in a specific subject area, to increase knowledge, but also to perform practical tasks and tasks that allow the formation of professional competence, such as logical thinking, creative activity, creative approach to mastering educational material [4].

Based on the definition of the concepts presented above, the following can be said, that is, "Independent work" or "Student's independent work" is a student's work organized in a certain form (calculation work, abstract, course work, course project, graduation work, master's thesis, thesis and articles, essays, case studies,

etc.). –Independent learning and independent work|| are the student's educational activities.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the transition to the credit-module system in higher education and giving ample space to the student's independent work in the course of studying this system is the main factor in the development of students' creative competencies. Independent work of students has an effective effect on the formation of a perfect human being in all fields of education (technical, construction, agriculture, medicine, law, pedagogy, culture, art and other fields).

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